

Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 1, 2025

The second law of thermodynamics deals with thermodynamic entropy, but it seems that for a uniform distribution in space (as for an ideal gas with no potential $V(x)$), the volume portion of entropy is information entropy. If one has volume V and another with $2V$, there are twice as many tiny cells in the $2V$ volume as in the V (assuming a uniform distribution). In other words, the number of states is twice as many and entropy is $-\ln(\text{number of states})$ in this case. This informational entropy in volume is linked to the second law of thermodynamics for the irreversible change of a box of V (by removing a partition) to one of $2V$. In other words, volume informational entropy increases.

Here, we consider a classical mechanics case of two particles in two one dimensional boxes, one of size L and the other of size $2L$. Each particle starts at $t=0$ at $x=0$ and moves with constant v , elastically bouncing off the wall. Each scenario is deterministic regardless of the size of the box. We now remove information about time, even though the scenario remains deterministic. We ask: Given a point x in the box L , to which point(s) does it map in the $2L$ box.? We find it maps to two possible points. For an L and $3L$, it maps to 3 etc. Thus, one sees that even in a deterministic case, with a piece of deterministic information t removed, one has the same notion of $2L$ containing twice the uncertainty as L .

As a check, we consider an x point in the $2L$ box and find that it maps back to a single point in the L box. In addition, however, there is a second $2L-x$ point in the $2L$ box which maps to the x point in the L box, so the reverse approach leads to the same conclusion.

Thermodynamic versus Informational Entropy

Thermodynamics deals with thermodynamic entropy, but for a uniform distribution in space, it seems that the volume entropy, proportional to $-\ln(V)$ is linked with informational entropy. In other words, one has twice as many little cells in $2V$ as in V . An irreversible removal of a barrier in a box of V allows the gas to occupy $2V$ automatically leading to more thermodynamic entropy which in this case seems to be informational entropy linked with $2V$ instead of V . This is in keeping with the second law of thermodynamics.

We ask: Does this notion of twice as much uncertainty in $2V$ (or $2L$) versus V (or L) already apply to a deterministic classical mechanics case for which one removes some information? We argue that it does.

Constant Velocity Classical Mechanics Scenario with Time Removed

Consider two boxes, one with length L and the other with $2L$ and let a particle in each start at $x=0$ at $t=0$ and move with speed v , elastically bouncing off the wall. For convenience, let $L=1$ and $2L=2$. This is now a set of deterministic classical mechanics scenarios and there is no notion of uncertainty or entropy. We next consider removing information about time. The motion is still deterministic, but one has no idea what the value of time is except that the same time holds for each particle. There is now informational uncertainty.

We first consider the box $L=1$ and place the particle at x . We ask: What is its time? As a simplification, let $v=1$. Then:

$$\text{Box } L=1: t = x + 2n \text{ or } t = 2-x+2n \quad ((1))$$

The question then becomes: To what does this map in the $L=2$ box?

$t=x+2n$ in the $L=1 \rightarrow$ for n even $x \rightarrow x$, for n odd, $x \rightarrow 2-x$ which is a different point

$t = 2-x + 2n$ in $L=1 \rightarrow$ for n even $x \rightarrow 2-x$, for n odd $x \rightarrow 2-x$

Thus, both sets of times, linked to a single x point in the $L=1$ box, map to the two distinct points: x and $2-x$ in the $L=2$ box ((2a))

In other words, if there is equal probability for the particle to be at any x in the $L=1$ box, then there is twice as much as uncertainty in the $L=2$ box, because each x point in the $L=1$ box has twice as much uncertainty in the $L=2$ box. This is strictly informational entropy for a deterministic classical mechanics case, but yields the same informational entropic results as for the volume entropy of an ideal gas.

Case of $L=1$ and $L=3$ etc

We next consider the case of an $L=1$ and $L=3$ box.

$$\text{Box } L=1: t = x + 2n$$

$$\text{Box } L=3 \quad n=0 \quad x \rightarrow x \quad n=1 \quad x \rightarrow 2+x \quad L=3 \text{ box} \quad n=2 \quad x \rightarrow 2-x \quad n=3 \quad x \rightarrow x \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{Box } L=1 \quad t = 2-x+2n$$

$$\text{Box } L=3 \quad n=0 \quad x \rightarrow 2-x \quad L=3 \text{ box}, \quad n=1 \quad x \rightarrow 2+x \quad n=2 \quad x \rightarrow x$$

Thus, x maps to three points: x , $2-x$ and $2+x$ in the $L=3$ box as expected.

For $L=4$

$$t=x+2n: \quad n=0 \quad x \rightarrow x, \quad n=1 \quad x \rightarrow x+2 \quad n=2 \quad x \rightarrow 4-x \quad n=3 \quad x \rightarrow 2-x \quad n=4 \quad x \rightarrow x$$

$$t=2-x+2n \quad n=0 \quad x \rightarrow 2-x, \quad n=1 \quad x \rightarrow 4-x \quad n=2 \quad x \rightarrow 2+x \quad n=3 \quad x \rightarrow x$$

Thus, x maps to 4 points, x , $2-x$, $4-x$ and $2+x$.

Reverse Mapping L=2 to L=1

We next consider the reverse mapping L=2 to L=1. If one has a point x in the L=2 box, then:

$$L=2 \text{ box: } t=x+4*n \text{ or } t=2+2-x+4*n \quad ((3))$$

For $t=x+4*n$ $x \rightarrow x$ in the L=1 box

For $t=2+2-x+4*n$ $x \rightarrow x$ in the L=1 box

We next note that $2-x$, a different point from x , in the L=2 box is linked with:

$$L=2 \text{ box: } t=2-x+4*n \text{ or } t=2+x+4*n$$

L=2 $t=2-x+4*n$ $2-x \rightarrow x$ in the L=1 box.

L=2 $t=2+x+4*n$ $2-x \rightarrow x$ in the L=1 box

Thus, two points, x and $2-x$ in the L=2 box map to the same x point in the L=1 box.

This is consistent with the L=2 box having twice as much uncertainty as the L=1 box.

Again one has the same informational entropy relation as in the thermodynamic case by removing time information from a deterministic classical mechanics problem.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue the volume entropy for an ideal gas seems to be informational if the uniform distribution applies (i.e. no potential $V(x)$). One may easily note that there are twice as many cells in $2V$ as in V , considering a uniform distribution. We ask: What happens in a deterministic classical mechanical situation? We consider the simplest case of two boxes, one with L=1 and the other with L=2. There is a particle in each at $x=0$, $t=0$ with a speed of 1. Each case is deterministic regardless of the size of the box. If one removes information about time, then we show that considering x in the L=1 size box to be distributed according to a uniform distribution, one may assign various times to x . These, however, map to two distinct points in the L=2 box. Thus, the L=2 box has twice as much uncertainty, even in the deterministic case with time removed. For L=3, one would have 3 times as much uncertainty. Thus, one may see informational entropy arising even in deterministic situations, we argue.